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The Innovative Searching for Booming Tokyo & Hong Kong Cities and Shanghai & Anhui Provinces GDP Enhancement Variations on Scientists Publishing in Subjects Information for Ph.D. by Sustainability

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Abstract

Primarily the new-power auto-maker sale situation may represent the industrial pillar one expressing much role and benefit for China to process continuously in future. Specially the new-green and low-contamination auto making will create the high-valuable product ie auto integrating system which needs several thousand parts to assembly in final work-shop through robotic non-tired working there. So that the additional robotic business for maker-shop user wil play more and more effectiveness currently and in near future whta request much labor and capital to complete its making technique. So, we have many working-opportunities for declining the non-employment rate meantime the more engineers and designers etc can be required for completing the industrial robot to proceed in auto-making shop with low-cost and high-efficiency. As for new emerging one the robotic working taken place human will be nearer and nearer in light of currently concluded situation and data. We should continuously develop that new tendency for the sake of decreasing the cost about lots of industrial robots making in fiscal & budget year. On the other hand, the reserved energy technique like chargeable batteries that may become boosting the new electrical generation that occupy an important position used in vehicles dynamic part. Thereby there would be more and more new technique to trial and make in factories as an important strategic plan in national views. Because of having its low-contamination purpose and high price-performance rate it will be easy to produce the dynamical part ie. electric engine's chargeable-battery although the controller will be difficult to understand by public. On the other side, those high-technology will enhance the GDP (gross domestic product) with certain degree besides the foreign trade transaction with exportation and importation will be enhanced by relevant government and enterprise units year by year. Certainly, the domestic producing amount will occupy definitely

hierarchy currently according to the Geely auto in December, 2025 the 6% will be for the BEVs (battery electric vehicles) and PHEVs (plug-in hybrid electric vehicles) and therein the 26% may be to exportation numbers. So, there would be still more space for Chinese auto maker to produce those electric vehicles with exporting more those ones anticipatively.

Keywords: booming economic GDP enhancement; Tokyo & Hong Kong; Chinese Shanghai & Anhui provinces; innovation search; scientist; sustainably; PhD

1. Introduction

The GDP (gross domestic product) which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. Like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence) ocean source space exploration etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~4]

2. Discussions

The GDP might be significant with exciting our scientist and engineers confidence for the sake of enhancing our high-technology product constantly with an innovation view. As knew it can take up new industrial innovative result for us to pursuit and grasp knowledge and experience armed by new technology spirituality which may last long time until next generation innovation exhibition completely and clearly. We can image the world one hundred years later we know some scenarios from the novel story and movies. There will be many ship-crafts that is to be created with advance technology and they fly from one place to another for the sake of completing save human mission. Maybe our earth-out-space & planet will be conquered somewhat so as to save earth resource and safe they have to transit into near planet for the reserving another route once the earth risk occurring we must get away the earth, or we will die in earth. No matter what will be we primarily seek to enhance our industrial product for promoting our GDP value, that is best way to want doing firstly. [5~6]

2.1 Introduction to the International Journal of Epidemiology and Public Health Research

Owning the Impact Factor of 3.2 as for the Doctor and Honorable Professor we extend a warm invitation to you to contribute an unpublished manuscript for publication in our upcoming issue. We are delighted to update you that IJEPHR is planning to release Volume 09 Issue 2 by the end of this month. Meantime, we can accept Research article/Review/Case Report/ Events/Pilot study or any type of article. Moreover, we would greatly appreciate it if you could submit your manuscript by January 20th, 2026. If your manuscript is prepared and ready for submission, please submit it via our email box with [online submission system](#). please note if you want to become a member of the Editorial Board, a minimum requirement of either a Ph.D. or M.D. is necessary. Your affirmative response to our invitation would be highly valued. At the end, we eagerly anticipate your submission. Welcoming the authors around the global writers give their noble papers to that journal for the sake of commonly developing. [1]

2.2 Subject for the Nanotechnology and Advanced Material Science

This is a Follow-Up mail regarding the Year End issue of the [Nanotechnology and Advanced Material Science \(ISSN: 2771-8050\)](#). Referring to your work "Convergence Proving of the Theoretical & True Elongation Inequalities by Derivation and Analogy". The Journal already have received 3 papers for the current Issue and we are inviting your paper so as to complete the Issue. I would like to check with you if you are interested to contribute in this Issue with a 1-2 page commentary or short review & research. You can directly submit the work in a Word document to [/researchopenworld.com/submissions/](#). Please let me know if you'd be interested in proceeding and let me know if you have any questions. We would like to invite all the authors having interest to our journal so

as to publish their noble papers with quickness and cheapness sincerely. [2]

2.3 Shanghai & Anhui province GDP analysis

The Shanghai & Beijing province GDP analysis in 2014~2015 would show 365~333 billion dollars by Shanghai city~Beijing one in 2015 in terms of Figure 1 expressed their high economy development status. Meanwhile, the y-y could show 7.2%~7% by them accordingly to show the up-middle development speed then. In contrast the Anhui province remained the 320 billion dollars with y-y 6.7% middle one existing in the lower position.

Figure 1. The Shanghai & Beijing province GDP analysis in 2014~2015. [3]

The Shanghai & Beijing province GDP analysis in 2007~2008 would show 206~165 billion dollars by Shanghai city~Beijing one in 2008 in terms of Figure 2 expressed their lower economy development status. Meanwhile, the y-y could show 6%~7.5% by them accordingly to show the middle development speed then. In contrast the Anhui province remained the 134 billion dollars with y-y 11% to be higher one.

Figure 2. The Shanghai & Beijing province GDP analysis in 2007~2008. [3]

2.4 Tokyo~Hong Kong GDP variations

The Tokyo~Hong Kong cities GDP status would show 862~167 billion dollars accordingly expressed the Tokyo city stronger economy situation and force in 1999 as exhibited in Figure 3. Meanwhile, the y-y value indicated 0.5%~0 by them indicated their cities lower development speed except that the Taiwan province retained 8.3% higher development speed.

Figure 3. The Shanghai & Beijing province GDP analysis in 2007~2008. [3]

On the other side, the Tokyo~Hong Kong cities GDP status would show 288~39 billion dollars accordingly expressed the Tokyo city stronger economy situation and force in 1985 as exhibited in Figure 4. Meantime, the y-y value indicated 15%~11% by them indicated their city increasing high development speed.

Figure 4. The Shanghai & Beijing province GDP analysis in 1984~1985. [3]

2.5 The China top 11~24 provinces' GDP analysis in 1979

The Heilongjiang~Jilin top 11~20 provinces GDP analysis in 1979 would show 3~1.3 billion dollars expressed the ones beyond 2 billion dollars were Hubei Hunan Zhejiang ones following Heilongjiang one respectively with 2.8~2.5 billion dollars to indicate the higher economy strength then in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The Heilongjiang~Jilin top 11~20 province GDP analysis in 1979. [3]

On the other side, the Guangxi~Fujian top 11~20 provinces GDP analysis in 1979 would show 1.34~1.2 billion dollars expressed the ones beyond 1 billion dollars were Shan'xi Chongqing ones following Guangxi one respectively with 1.33~1.2 billion dollars to indicate the high economy strength then in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The Guangxi~Fujian top 21~24 provinces GDP analysis in 1979. [3]

Overview, we will collaborate closely with cross-functional teams to identify emerging trends and validate hypotheses through iterative experimentation. The leverage shared insights to refine technical frameworks, ensuring alignment between theoretical advancements and practical applications. Meantime, shall integrate feedback loops for continuous improvement, enhancing the adaptability of solutions in dynamic environments. So that we should advocate the positive tactic to foster the excellent preparation team to gain the prize item like Nobel prize laureates that releases the Physics Chemistry & Physiology Medicine items by the Swedish Royal Academy of Science and Karolinska Institute each year respectively. They are going to become the leadership at the related cutting-edge field. [7~15]

3. Conclusions

The high-level scholars like scientist and experts has possessed the ability around reforming current technique barrier whose excellent ones may gain the Nobel prize about six~ten every year to show the new phenomenon and theory sustainably. Thereby they become the leader position in world scientific activity. So that we should cultivate more those scientists in each cutting-edge field prepared to be selected by Swedish royal academy of sciences and Karolinska Institute release the Physics and Chemistry & Physiology and Medicine respectively. On the other side, the national & regional GDP with different ones can monitor the entire economy activities within one year and more than one year like ten years. As for enhancing that one the economy activities including consuming business behavior and working at advance factories for earning money and even retirement salary simultaneously. Thereby the working position will become an important thing for us to earn more money for the sake of using after retirement. Certainly, our consuming behavior can increase the goods quantity and quality that may activate economic thriving one. Thereby enhancing GDP has to promote high-technology product with owning a better beneficial price for us to earn more money for stabilizing our old years. Please try to consider if one has no enough money how he may live normally and happily many years later, hereby we must put our capital into the Social Security Bureau with enough money and time more than 20 years. At the same time the scientist must write their

papers continually to famed journal so as to maintain some achievement in research activity. Hence, he may acquire titled as an academician in China academy of Science & Engineering maintaining a permanent title which may carry out bonus permanently per month after he becomes old. We must continually process our research on innovation field to find new phenomenon and project in detail subject. Don't forget to cooperate with others already grasping some internal cause-effect relation to enlarge the relevant skill into products which may bring in new wind on the searching route of technology.

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Ethic Declarations

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest.

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